

Minor Project on:
Design and Optimization of Shell & Tube Heat Exchanger Using
Aspen Exchanger Design and Rating (EDR)

Report submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of
B.Tech.

In
Chemical Engineering

Under the Supervision of

Professor A.K Jain

By

Pravind Kumar Thakur
[Enrollment Number: 03016101420]

University School of Chemical Technology
Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University
Dwarka Sec- 16C, Delhi- 110078

Certificate

This is to certify that the project report titled " Design and Optimization of Shell & Tube Heat Exchanger Using Aspen Exchanger Design and Rating (EDR)" submitted to University School of Chemical Technology, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi in fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Bachelor of Engineering in Chemical Engineering embodies the original research work carried out by Pravind Kumar Thakur under the supervision of Prof. A.K Jain and Asst. Prof. Shweta Gupta. This work has not been submitted in part or full for any degree or diploma to this or any other University.

Pravind Kumar Thakur

Enrollment No.: 03016101420

Supervisor: Prof. A.K Jain (Dean, USCT)

Declaration

I hereby declare that the project report titled “ Design and Optimization of Shell & Tube Heat Exchanger Using Aspen Exchanger Design and Rating (EDR)” is an authentic record of the research work conducted by me and is free from any falsification and plagiarism. This work was carried out under the supervision of Prof. A.K Jain and Asst. Prof. Shweta Gupta at University School of Chemical Technology, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi. I assume full responsibility for any disputes that may arise from the content of my research work.

Pravind Kumar Thakur

Enrollment No.: 03016101420

Acknowledgment

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Student Name: Pravind Kumar Thakur

Student enrollment No.: 03016101420

Student Signature:

Content

Certificate

Declaration

Acknowledgement

Content

List of Figures

List of Tables

Notations

Abstract

Chapter 1: Introduction

1

Chapter 2: Design parameters

- 2.1 Shell
- 2.2 Tube
- 2.3 Baffles
- 2.4 Tube Sheets
- 2.5 Tube Pitch
- 2.6 Tube Bundles
- 2.7 Fouling
- 2.8 Allocation of Streams

Chapter 3: Design Codes

- 3.1 TEMA
 - 3.1.1 TEMA Class for Channels
 - 3.1.2 Selection of heads
 - 3.1.3 Selection of Shell
- 3.2 Case Selection TEMA types
 - 3.2.1 TEMA types involving A, B, C, D, L, M, and N
 - 3.2.2 TEMA designations involving L, M and N as 3rd character
 - 3.2.3 TEMA types involving F, G, and H as 2nd character
 - 3.2.4 TEMA types with U as 3rd character

Chapter 4: Theory-Kern's method

Chapter 5: Simulation

- 5.1 Evaluating Constraints
- 5.2 Initial Geometry
- 5.3 Aspen EDR
- 5.4 Process simulation
- 5.5 Problem Statement

Reference

List of Figures

S. No.	Figure Caption	Page number
1.1	Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger	
2.1	Types of Baffles	
2.2	Flowing Pattern in Baffles	
2.3	Tube Sheet Patterns	
5.1	Screen shot of the crude distillation unit with heat exchanger E-100 as the basis for rating/checking design calculations from the PFD in the Simulation Environment (Source: UniSim Design R443, Courtesy of Honeywell Process Solutions).	

List of Tables

S. No.	Title	Page number
1.1	Representative values of overall heat transfer coefficient in heat exchanger	
2.1	Value of K1 and n	
2.2	Fouling Characteristics	
3.1	Selection of Heads	
3.2	Selection of Shell	
3.3	Baffle types as per TEMA	

Notations

A	Area (m ²)
A _s	Cross Flow Area (m ²)
B	Baffle Spacing (m)
C	Specific Heat Capacity (J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
D _b	Bundle Diameter (m)
D _i	Inside diameter of shell (m)
D _s	Outside diameter of shell (m)
d _e	Equivalent Diameter (m)
d _i	Inside diameter of tube (m)
d _o	Outside diameter of tube (m)
F	Fouling Factor.
F _t	Log Mean Temperature Difference Correction Factor
h	Enthalpy (J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
h _i	Tube side Film Heat Transfer Coefficient (W m ⁻² K ⁻¹)
h _s	Shell side Film Heat Transfer Coefficient (W m ⁻² K ⁻¹)
J _f	Friction Factor
J _h	Heat Transfer Factor
k	Thermal Conductivity, Turbulent kinetic energy.
L	Length (m) m Mass Flow Rate (kg s ⁻¹)
N	Number of tubes.
N _p	Number of tube side passes
P _{in}	Pressure at inlet of the shell
P _{out}	Pressure at outlet of the shell
ΔP	Pressure Drop. Pt Pitch.
Q	Heat Load.
ΔT _{lm}	Log Mean Temperature Difference.
t	Time.
U	Overall Heat Transfer Factor.

Abstract

This project delves into the meticulous design of a Shell & tube Heat Exchanger using Aspen EDR, with a keen focus on its industrial implications. The paramount objective is to harness cutting-edge engineering principles and technological advancements to optimize heat exchange processes in real-world industrial applications.

Under the expert guidance of Prof. A.K Jain, a distinguished authority in the field of Chemical Engineering at Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, the project unfolds a comprehensive exploration of heat exchanger design methodologies. The utilization of Aspen EDR software adds a practical dimension to the endeavor, aligning theoretical knowledge with industry-relevant tools.

The project aims to contribute novel insights and innovative solutions applicable to diverse industries, including but not limited to petrochemical, energy, and manufacturing sectors.

Furthermore, collaboration with industry professionals and experts has been integral to this research, ensuring alignment with contemporary industrial standards and practices. Insights gained from this project are anticipated to have a substantial impact on the optimization of heat exchange systems within industrial settings, enhancing overall efficiency and sustainability.

This abstract encapsulates a multifaceted approach, integrating academic rigor with practical industrial relevance, and underscores the project's potential to advance the field of heat exchanger design within an industrial framework.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Heat exchangers play a pivotal role in the efficient transfer of thermal energy between fluids at different temperatures, contributing to various industrial applications. Common examples of heat exchangers include automobile radiators, condensers, evaporators, air preheaters, and oil coolers. Their widespread use is evident in power plants, petroleum industries, heating, ventilation, refrigeration, and air conditioning systems (HVAC), heat recovery systems, and the chemical process industry.

In power plants and diverse engineering processes, heat exchangers, including intercoolers, boilers, pre-heaters, and condensers, are crucial for controlling heat energy. These devices facilitate efficient heat transfer and can be broadly classified into recuperative and regenerative types. Recuperative heat exchangers exchange heat on either side of a dividing wall by fluids, while regenerative heat exchangers have hot and cold fluids in the same space, employing a matrix of materials alternately as a source for heat flow.

Optimal thermal design of shell & tube heat exchangers involves a meticulous consideration of various interacting design parameters. The design process encompasses both process and mechanical aspects.

Process Considerations:

1. Assigning process fluids to the shell side or tube side.
2. Selecting stream temperature specifications.
3. Defining shell side and tube side pressure drop design limits.
4. Establishing shell side and tube side velocity limits.
5. Choosing heat transfer models and fouling coefficients for both shell side and tube side.

Mechanical Considerations:

1. Selecting the heat exchanger TEMA layout and determining the number of passes.
2. Specifying tube parameters, including size, layout, pitch, and material.
3. On tube length setting upper and lower limits.
4. Specifying shell side parameters such as materials, baffles cut, baffle spacing, and clearances.
5. Establishing upper and lower design limits on shell diameter, baffle cut, and baffle spacing.

The integration of these considerations ensures a comprehensive and efficient thermal design, aligning with the specific requirements of industrial applications. This project explores the multifaceted nature of shell & tube heat exchangers, addressing their crucial role in diverse industries and highlighting the intricate design parameters involved.

1.1. Heat Transfer Processes:

Heat exchanger is a device designed to transfer thermal energy between two or more fluids, and the heat transfer process involves distinct stages:

Convection from Hot Fluid to Wall:

The initial stage involves the transfer of heat from the hot fluid to the wall of the heat exchanger through convection. In this process, the high-temperature fluid near the wall imparts its thermal energy to the adjacent solid surface.

Conduction Through the Wall:

Once the heat is transferred to the wall, the thermal energy traverses through the wall material via conduction. The wall acts as a medium, allowing the efficient flow of heat from the hot side to the cold side.

Convection from Wall to Cold Fluid:

Subsequently, the thermal energy reaches the cold side of the heat exchanger, where it is transferred to the cold fluid through convection. The cold fluid gains heat as it absorbs the energy released by the wall, completing the heat transfer cycle.

In essence, the combination of convection, conduction, and convection again facilitates the exchange of thermal energy between the two fluids while maintaining a physical separation through the heat exchanger wall.

The total amount of thermal resistance involved with the heat transfer process involves two convection and one conduction resistances. Total thermal resistance become,

$$R = \frac{1}{h_i A_i} + \frac{\ln(D_o/D_i)}{2\pi k L} + \frac{1}{h_o A_o} \quad ; \text{ Where}$$

A_o = surface area of outer surface of the wall

A_i = surface area of inner surface of the wall

So, the heat transfer through the pipe is:

$$q = \frac{T_A - T_B}{\frac{1}{h_i A_i} + \frac{\ln(D_o/D_i)}{2\pi k L} + \frac{1}{h_o A_o}}$$

When analyzing heat exchangers, it is advantageous to consolidate all thermal resistances along the heat flow path from the hot fluid to the cold one into a unified resistance denoted as R. This allows for the expression of the rate of heat transfer between the two fluids.

$$Q = \frac{\Delta T}{R} = U A \Delta T = U_i A_i \Delta T = U_o A_o \Delta T$$

where U is the overall heat transfer coefficient, (unit is $W/m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$), which is identical to the unit of the ordinary convection coefficient h. Canceling T, Equation reduces to

$$\frac{1}{U A_s} = \frac{1}{U_i A_i} = \frac{1}{U_o A_o} = R = \frac{1}{h_i A_i} + R_{wall} + \frac{1}{h_o A_o}$$

Type of heat exchanger	Units U, ($W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$)
Water to water	850-1700
Water to oil	100-350
Water to gasoline or kerosene	300-1000
Feed water heater	1000-8500
Steam to light fuel oil	200-400
Steam condenser	1000-600
Freon condenser(water cooled)	300-1000
Ammonia condenser(water cooled)	800-1400
Alcohol condenser(water cooled)	250-700
Gas to gas	10-40
Water to air finned tubes(water in tubes)	30-60 400-850
Steam to air in finned tubes(steam in tubes)	30-300 400-4000

Table 1.1: Representative values of overall heat transfer coefficient in heat exchanger

Figure 1.1: Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

1. Shell	16. Tubes (U-type)
2. Shell cover	17. Tie rods and spacers
3. Shell flange (channel end)	18. Transverse (or cross) baffles or support plates
4. Shell flange (cover end)	19. Longitudinal baffles
5. Shell nozzle or branch	20. Impingement baffles
6. Floating tube sheet	21. Floating head support
7. Floating head cover	22. Pass partition
8. Floating head flange	23. Vent connection
9. Floating head gland	24. Drain connection
10. Floating head backing ring	25. Instrument connection
11. Stationary tube sheet	26. Expansion bellows
12. Channel or stationary head	27. Support saddles
13. Channel cover	28. Lifting lugs
14. Channel nozzle or branch	29. Weir
15. Tube (straight)	30. Liquid level connection

1.2. Types of Heat Exchangers:

Transfer of heat from one fluid to another is a vital process in the majority of chemical industries. The primary application of heat transfer lies in the design of equipment dedicated to exchanging heat between two fluids, commonly referred to as Heat Exchangers. These devices, designed for the efficient transfer of heat, are generally classified based on the specific transfer processes occurring within them, as illustrated in Figure 1.1.

Among the various types of heat exchangers, **shell & tube heat exchangers emerge as the most widely used heat exchange equipment.** The common types of shell & shell & tube heat exchangers include:

Fixed Tube-Sheet Exchanger (Non-Removable Tube Bundle):

This is the simplest and most cost-effective type of shell & shell & tube heat exchanger with a fixed tube sheet design. In this configuration, the tube sheet is welded to the shell, preventing any relative movement between the shell & tube bundle (refer to Figure 1.2).

Removable Tube Bundle Exchanger:

Tube bundles in these exchangers can be removed for ease of cleaning and replacement. This category includes floating-head and U-tube exchangers.

Floating-Head Exchanger: Features a stationary tube sheet clamped with the shell flange. At the opposite end of the bundle, tubes may expand into a freely riding floating head or floating tube sheet. The floating head cover is bolted to the tube sheet, allowing the entire bundle to be removed for cleaning and inspection (depicted in Figure 1.3).

U-Tube Exchanger: Consists of tubes bent in the form of a 'U' and rolled back into the tube sheet, as shown in Figure 1.4. This design may omit some tubes at the center of the tube bundle, and the tubes can expand freely towards the 'U' bend end.

Guidelines for the mechanical design of unfired shell & tube heat exchangers are provided by TEMA (USA) and IS: 4503-1967 (India) standards.

Chapter 2

Design Parameters

The Thermal design of a shell & tube heat exchanger encompasses several critical parameters, including the determination of heat transfer area, number of tubes, tube length and diameter, tube layout, number of shell & tube passes, heat exchanger type (fixed tube sheet, removable tube bundle, etc.), tube pitch, number of baffles, their type and size, and shell & tube side pressure drop.

2.1. Shell: The shell serves as the container for the shell fluid, with the tube bundle positioned inside. Selection of the shell diameter aims for a close fit of the tube bundle. The clearance between the tube bundle and the inner shell wall depends on the type of exchanger ([2]; page 647). Shells are typically fabricated from standard steel pipe with an adequate corrosion allowance. For operating pressures up to 300 psi and a shell ID of 12-24 inches, a shell thickness of 3/8 inch is deemed satisfactory.

2.2. Tube: Commonly, tube outer diameters of 3/4 and 1 inch are employed in designing compact heat exchangers. Optimal heat transfer conditions involve maximizing the number of tubes in the shell to enhance turbulence. Tube thickness must be sufficient to withstand internal pressure, considering the necessary corrosion allowance. Tube thickness is expressed in terms of BWG (Birmingham Wire Gauge) and true outside diameter (OD). Tube lengths of 6, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 feet are preferred, although longer tubes reduce shell diameter at the expense of higher shell pressure drop. Finned tubes come into play when fluids with low heat transfer coefficients flow on the shell side. Stainless steel, admiralty brass, copper, bronze, and copper-nickel alloys are common materials used for tubes.

2.3. Baffles: Baffles play a crucial role in supporting tubes, maintaining a desirable fluid velocity at the shell side, and preventing tube failure due to flow-induced vibration. There are two primary types of baffles: plate and rod. Plate baffles can be single-segmental, double-segmental, or triple-segmental.

The shell side crossflow area (a_s) is determined by the formula:

$$a_s = (D.C.B)/P_T$$

Where:

(a_s) is the shell side crossflow area,

(D) is the shell inside diameter,

(C) is the clearance between tubes,

(B) is the baffle spacing,

(P_T) is the tube pitch.

Baffle Spacing: The minimum baffle spacing (pitch) should generally not be closer than 1/5 of the shell diameter (ID) or 2 inches, whichever is greater. The maximum spacing does not normally exceed the shell diameter. Tube support plate spacing is determined by mechanical considerations, such as strength and vibration.

Maximum Spacing: The maximum spacing is given by mechanical considerations and aims to prevent failures, especially when the unsupported tube length is greater than 80%. Designers often limit the shell side pressure drop.

Baffle Cuts: It is a segment cut away to permit the fluid to flow parallel to the tube axis as it flows from one baffle space to another. Baffle cuts can vary between 15% and 45% and are expressed as the ratio of segment opening height to shell inside diameter. The upper limit ensures that every pair of baffles adequately supports each tube. Kern shell side pressure drop correlations are commonly based on a 25% cut, standard for liquid on the shell side.

Baffle Clearances: The outer tube limit (OTL) is the diameter created by encircling the outermost tubes in a tube layout. The actual OTL is usually 1.5 times the design pressure, used during a hydrostatic test to detect leaks at any joint on the heat exchanger.

Example Fixed Tube-Sheet Clearances:

$$\{\text{Shell Inside Diameter (mm)}\} = \{\text{Clearance Shell I.D and OTL (mm)}\}$$

$$- 254 (10) \text{ to } 610 (24) \rightarrow 11 (7/16)$$

$$- \geq 635 (25) \rightarrow 13 (1/2)$$

Figure 2.1: Types of Baffles

Doughnut and Disc Type Baffles

Double Segmental Transverse Baffles

Single Segmental Transverse Baffles

Figure 2.2: Flowing Patterns in baffles

2.4. Tube Sheets: Tube sheets, crucial in shell-and-tube heat exchangers, are flat, round metal pieces with precisely drilled and reamed holes. Tubes are securely attached using methods like hydraulic pressure or roller expansion. Machining grooves in tube holes enhances joint strength.

Purpose: Tube sheets serve as plates with holes for tube insertion.

Securing Tubes: Tubes are firmly attached to prevent fluid mixing between shell & tubesides.

2.5. Tube Pitch: The distance between tube holes, usually 1.25 times the tube diameter, optimizes arrangement for efficient heat transfer. **It is defined by $P_T = d_0 + C$**

Figure 2.3: Tube Sheet Patterns

2.6. Tube Bundles: Tube bundles, also known as tube stacks, are designed to meet specific customer needs and can replace existing units. Two common types are the Fixed Tube Sheet and U-Tube configurations.

a) Fixed Tube Sheet: Straight tubes secured at both ends by tube sheets welded to the shell.

Application: Suitable for various heat exchange applications.

b) U-Tube: Tubes bent in a U-shape with only one tube sheet in the heat exchanger.

Application: Offers versatility and efficiency in certain heat transfer scenarios.

The bundle diameter (Db) can be estimated using the formula:

$$D_b = d_o (N_t / K_1)^{1/n}$$

Where:

(do): Tube Outside Diameter

(N_t): Number of tubes

(K₁) and (n): Constants (Value given in table below)

Triangular Pitch $p_t = 1.25 d_o$					
Number Passes	1	2	4	6	8
K ₁	0.319	0.249	0.175	0.0743	0.0365
n	2.142	2.207	2.285	2.499	2.675
Square Pitch $p_t = 1.25 d_o$					
Number Passes	1	2	4	6	8
K ₁	0.215	0.156	0.158	0.0402	0.0331
n	2.207	2.291	2.263	2.617	2.643

Figure 2.1: Value of k1 and n

2.7. Fouling: In heat exchangers, fouling, the accumulation of unwanted materials on processing equipment surfaces, poses significant challenges impacting both performance and efficiency. The fouling layer, characterized by low thermal conductivity, increases heat transfer resistance and diminishes the overall effectiveness of heat exchangers. This phenomenon is particularly problematic as it necessitates additional energy consumption and maintenance costs. Frequent fouling results in increased construction expenses due to the need for oversizing, and regular cleaning becomes imperative for optimal functionality. Additionally, fouling is considered in the heat exchanger design by incorporating tube side and shell side fouling resistances, mitigating the associated performance limitations.

On the other hand, vibrations induced by fluid flow in heat exchangers present practical problems that require careful consideration. Various vibration mechanisms, including fluid elastic instability (Critical flow velocity causing instability), vortex shedding (Periodic shedding of vortices can damage tubes), acoustic resonance (Occurs when acoustic wave frequency aligns with tube natural frequency), turbulent buffering (Significant in two-phase flow situations), and flow pulsation (Periodic variations in flow become crucial in two-phase flow scenarios), can compromise the integrity of the

heat exchanger tubes. Effective strategies such as adjusting span lengths, altering tube diameter, and implementing deresonating baffles are employed to counteract these vibration challenges. A comprehensive understanding of both fouling and vibration issues is essential for the successful design, operation, and maintenance of heat exchangers, ensuring prolonged and efficient functionality.

Fluid	Coefficient ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{°C}^{-1}$)	Resistance ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{°C}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$)
River water	3000-12,000	0.0003-0.0001
Sea water	1000-3000	0.001-0.0003
Cooling water (towers)	3000-6000	0.0003-0.00017
Towns water (soft)	3000-5000	0.0003-0.0002
Towns water (hard)	1000-2000	0.001-0.0005
Steam condensate	1500-5000	0.00067-0.0002
Steam (oil free)	4000- 10,000	0.0025-0.0001
Steam (oil traces)	2000-5000	0.0005-0.0002
Refrigerated brine	3000-5000	0.0003-0.0002
Air and industrial gases	5000-10,000	0.0002-0.0001
Flue gases	2000-5000	0.0005-0.0002
Organic vapors	5000	0.0002
Organic liquids	5000	0.0002
Light hydrocarbons	5000	0.0002
Heavy hydrocarbons	2000	0.0005
Boiling organics	2500	0.0004
Condensing organics	5000	0.0002
Heat transfer fluids	5000	0.0002
Aqueous salt solutions	3000-5000	0.0003-0.0002

Figure 2.2: Fouling Characteristics

2.8. Allocation of Streams:

- **High Pressure:** When one stream operates at high pressure, it is advantageous to position that stream inside the tubes. This design choice allows for a focus on designing only the tubes and tube-side fittings to withstand high pressure, while the shell can be constructed with lighter-weight materials.
- **Corrosion:** The material selection for construction is often dictated by corrosion considerations. To minimize costs, especially when corrosion-resistant alloys are more expensive, the corrosive fluid is typically placed inside the tubes, avoiding the need for corrosion-resistant alloys on the shell side.
- **Viscosity:** Highly viscous fluids are placed on the shell side to induce turbulence by incorporating baffles in the shell. This arrangement helps enhance heat transfer efficiency.
- **Fouling:** While fouling influences the design of most process exchangers, streams prone to severe fouling necessitate design features that minimize fouling or facilitate easier cleaning.
- **Low Heat Transfer Coefficient:** Streams with inherently low heat transfer coefficients, such as low-pressure gases or viscous liquids, are preferably placed on the shell side.
- **Flow Rate:** Generally, fluids with smaller flow rates are positioned on the shell side. This arrangement allows for the provision of adequate turbulence by increasing the number of baffles.
- **Phase of Fluid:** Two-phase fluids are placed on the shell side as part of the design consideration.

Chapter 3

Design Code

3.1. TEMA: (Standards of Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association) These guidelines are designed to complement and elucidate the ASME Pressure Vessel Code specifically for shell-and-tube exchanger applications (excluding double-pipe exchangers). While TEMA is intricately linked with ASME VIII, it serves as a valuable standard that can augment various national codes beyond ASME. Construction recommendations are delineated in three distinct classes, with the specific class being designated by the purchaser. It is essential to note that the design rules remain consistent across all classes, with variations confined to dimensions and construction details.

Class R: Tailored for the rigorous requirements typically encountered in petroleum and related processing applications.

Class C: Geared towards the generally moderate requirements prevalent in commercial and general process services.

Class B: Specifically designed for chemical process service.

The numbering system employed is uniform across all classes, and TEMA references indicate whether they pertain to Class R, C, or B of the 1978 edition. This edition marks a notable inclusion of a section titled "Recommended Good Practice," addressing aspects not covered in the primary sections of the standard. It particularly focuses on the requisites for exchangers featuring shell diameters ranging from 1524 to 2540 mm (60 to 100 inches). The numbering system aligns with the three main sections of TEMA, with an asterisk (*) consistently denoting additional recommended good practices.

This comprehensive framework ensures a standardized approach to the design and construction of shell-and-tube exchangers, offering flexibility to cater to diverse industry needs while maintaining a consistent and robust set of design rules.

3.1.1. TEMA Class for Channels:

TEMA Class for Channels	Application
R	Severe requirements of petroleum and related process applications.
C	Moderate requirements of commercial and general process applications.
B	Chemical process service.

TEMA Front and Rear Ends:

TEMA Front Head

TEMA Rear Head

3.1.2. Selection of Heads (Table 3.1):

TEMA Front Head Selection	
A	Easy to open for tube side access. For low pressure applications.
B	For Higher-pressure applications, preferred with clean tube side fluid. It is less expensive than Type A.
C	Tube side is corrosive, toxic or hazardous and when removable tube bundle is required. It is normally used for low-pressure operations.
N	For application where tube side is corrosive, toxic or hazardous and shell side fluid is clean and any leakage possibility is to be eliminated.
D	Very High-pressure applications.

TEMA Rear Head Selection	
L, M, N	Fixed Head, should be used when thermal differential expansion of the shell and tubes is low and shell side fluid is clean.
L	For low pressure applications.
M	For Higher-pressure applications, not requiring frequent maintenance.
N	For application where tube side is Corrosive, toxic or hazardous and where leakage of shell to tube side fluid and vice versa, is to be eliminated.
U	For thermal differential expansion of the shell and tubes is higher and tube side fluid is clean. For highpressure applications or, with hazardous/ toxic fluid on shell side.
P, S, T, W	Should be used when shell side fluid or both shell & tubeside fluid are Dirty.

P	Pressure is low and shell side fluid is not toxic or hazardous. Where risk of internal flange leakage is to be avoided.
S	Normal Pressure requirements, relatively lesser maintenance requirements.
T	High-pressure requirements, frequent need to takeout the tube bundle.
W	For low-pressure application.

TEMA Shell Types:

Common TEMA type of Shell & Tube Heat Exchangers: AES, BEU, BHU, BXU, BEM, AKU, AET, AEL

3.1.3. Selection of Shell (Table 3.2):

TEMA Shell Selection	
E	The E shell is the most common as it is inexpensive and simple.
F	F shell is rarely used in practice because there are many problems associated with the design. It is difficult to remove/replace the tube bundle, problems of fabrication and maintenance, internal leakage, unbalanced thermal expansion in case of large temperature difference between inlet & outlet.
G, H	To accommodate high inlet velocities. They are used as horizontal thermosiphon reboilers, condensers, and other phase-change applications.
J	Used for low pressure drop applications such as a condenser in vacuum.
K	The K shell is used for partially vaporizing the shell fluid. It is used as a kettle reboiler in the process industry and as a flooded chiller in the refrigeration industry. They are used when essentially 100% vaporization is required.
X	It is used for gas heating and cooling and for vacuum condensation. It is also used when shell flows are large.

3.2. Case Selection of TEMA Types:

Front end stationary head types		Shell types		Rear end head types	
A	<p>Channel and removable cover</p>	E	<p>One-pass shell</p>	L	<p>Fixed tubesheet like "A" stationary head</p>
B	<p>Bonnet (Integral cover)</p>	F	<p>Two-pass shell with longitudinal baffle</p>	M	<p>Fixed tubesheet like "B" stationary head</p>
C	<p>Removable tube bundle only</p> <p>Channel integral with tube-sheet and removable cover</p>	G	<p>Split flow</p>	N	<p>Fixed tubesheet like "N" stationary head</p>
N	<p>Channel integral with tube-sheet and removable cover</p>	H	<p>Double-split flow</p>	P	<p>Outside packed Floating head</p>
D	<p>Special High-pressure closure</p>	J	<p>Divided flow</p>	S	<p>Floating head with backing device</p>
		K	<p>Kettle-type reboiler</p>	T	<p>Pull through floating head</p>
		X	<p>Cross-flow</p>	U	<p>U-Tube bundle</p>
				W	<p>Externally sealed floating tubesheet</p>

3.2.1 TEMA types involving A, B, C, D, L, M, and N (1st and 3rd character):

Selection among the types characterized by the above letters will normally be based on mechanical and operational aspects. They will not affect the calculations performed by HEATEX87.

When dealing with high-pressure exchangers (above 80-100 kg/cm²) only Type D must be specified. The Mechanical Department will then select an appropriate design which may not necessarily have the appearance as shown in TEMA.

3.2.2 TEMA designations involving L, M and N as 3rd character (Fixed tube sheet):

The above refers to a design where the connections between the tube sheets and the shell are fixed. This is a relatively cheap construction, which moreover in many cases allows true counter current flow. On the other hand, mechanical cleaning on the shell side will not be possible. Furthermore, the fixed connection between tube sheet and shell means that tubes and shell cannot expand independently of each other. Normally expansion bellows are not acceptable for this purpose. During the following engineering steps, it shall therefore be verified if the allowable stresses are within allowable limits.

3.2.3 TEMA types involving F, G, and H as 2nd character (longitudinal baffles):

These types are chosen because they often provide a greater degree of countercurrent flow than other acceptable alternatives. However, they will only perform satisfactorily if the longitudinal baffle is properly sealed to the shell. Such seals are very vulnerable to damage during mounting and dismantling. Furthermore, longitudinal baffles are often exposed to pressure drops many times bigger than those of normal baffles. TEMA types with T and S as 3rd character (floating head) These types normally allow the tube bundle to be pulled out of the shell, thus allowing mechanical cleaning on both shell side and tube side. At the same time, they allow greater differential expansions between shell and tubes. However, it is a rather complicated and expensive construction, in particular in case the head shall be designed for a big differential pressure. Moreover, control of the internal flange tightness will not be possible during operation. The above types also require a big space between shell & tube bundle. Efficient blocking of this space with sealing strips is in case of segmental baffles mandatory to ensure a reasonable performance on the shell side.

3.2.4 TEMA types with U as 3rd character (U-tubes):

This type stands for U-tubes. It results in a relatively cheap construction. However, there are certain limitations to the application of this type. It is not possible to clean the tube side efficiently by mechanical means. This construction should therefore be used only for non-fouling services.

Interrelation between cross flow baffle type and TEMA type It should be kept in mind that the baffle type is to be selected with due consideration to the TEMA type. As guidance, the following table should be used:

	<u>I</u>	<u>II</u>	<u>III</u>	
TEMA Type	Segmental	Double segmental	Disc and doughnut	Relative Volumetric capacity
E	1	1	1	2
F	2 v	1 h, v	4	1
G	3 v	1 h	4	2
H	3 v	1 h	4	3
J	1	3	3	3
X	1	1 *	4	4

Table 3.3:: Baffle type as per TEMA

Chapter 4

Theory- Kern's Method

Codes and standards are applicable only for mechanical design/aspects of shell & tube heat exchanger but w.r.t process design we do not have any standards but some definite methods. The steps for designing according to this base method are:

Chapter 5

Simulation

Designing Shell & tube Heat Exchanger in ASPEN Exchanger Design Rating (EDR):

5.1. Evaluating Constraints:

Thermal evaluation: Parting from the heat transfer developed: Convection (tube fluid) + Conduction (through pipe thickness) + Convection (Shell fluid).

$$Q = (m C_p \Delta T)$$

$$Q = U_{Req} A F (\Delta T_{ln})_{cf}$$

where

$$U_{Req} = \frac{Q}{A F (\Delta T_{ln})_{cf}}$$

$$Q = U_{clean} A \Delta T_m$$

where

$$U_{clean} = \left(\frac{D_o}{h_i D_i} + \frac{D_o \ln(D_o/D_i)}{2k} + \frac{1}{h_o} \right)^{-1}$$

U_{clean} is used when the Heat Exchanger is new. While U_D is used when dirt or scale appears.

$$Q = U_D A F (\Delta T_{ln})_{cf}$$

$$U_D = \left(\frac{D_o}{h_i D_i} + \frac{D_o \ln(D_o/D_i)}{2k} + \frac{1}{h_o} + \frac{R_{Di} D_o}{D_i} + R_{Do} \right)^{-1}$$

To be thermally stable, the overall co-efficient must: $U_{clean} > U_D > U_{Req}$

Thermal Evaluation Diagram Flow:

Hydraulic Assessment: It is imperative that the combined total pressure drop on the tube and shell sides remains within the permissible limit. Upon selecting the initial heat exchanger geometry, the subsequent equations (applicable when using English Units) are employed to verify whether the chosen geometry aligns with the allowable pressure drop limits.

Tube Side $\Delta P_{tubes} = \Delta P_f + \Delta P_r + \Delta P_n$

$$\Delta P_f = \frac{f n_p L G^2}{(7,50 * 10^{12}) D_i s \phi}$$

$$\Delta P_r = 1,334 * 10^{-13} \alpha_r G^2 / s \quad (\text{Velocity Head})$$

Nozzles ΔP { $\Delta P_n = 2 * 10^{-13} N_s G_n^2 / s$ (Turbulent flow)
 $\Delta P_n = 4 * 10^{-13} N_s G_n^2 / s$ (Laminar flow)

α_r		
Flow Regime	Regular Tubes	U-tubes
Turbulent	$2Np-1.5$	$1.6Np-1.5$
Laminar	$3.25Np-1.5$	$2.38Np-1.5$

Shell side $\Delta P_{shell} = \Delta P_f + \Delta P_n$

$$\Delta P_f = \frac{f G^2 d_s (n_b + 1)}{(7,50 * 10^{12}) d_e s \phi}$$

Nozzles ΔP { $\Delta P_n = 2 * 10^{-13} N_s G_n^2 / s$ (Turbulent flow)
 $\Delta P_n = 4 * 10^{-13} N_s G_n^2 / s$ (Laminar flow)

For a suitable Heat Exchanger evaluation

$$\Delta P_{tubes,allowed} > \Delta P_{tubes}$$

$$\Delta P_{shell,allowed} > \Delta P_{shell}$$

Several factors influence the pressure drop in a heat exchanger, impacting both the tube and shell sides. On the tube side, factors such as tube length (L) and the number of tube passes (np) play crucial roles. For the shell side, baffle spacing (B) is a significant determinant; an increase in baffle spacing enhances the flow area across the tube bundle, leading to a reduction in shell-side pressure drop (ΔP_{shell}). Additionally, tube pitch (PT) is considered, although it is not commonly utilized due to its tendency to escalate heat exchanger area and, consequently, increase costs. These factors bear significance in the design process, whether conducted manually or through computer-aided software. If the initially selected geometry fails to meet pressure drop requirements, adjustments to these influencing factors become imperative to achieve a suitable heat exchanger design.

5.2. Initial geometry:

1	
FLUID PLACEMENT(TUBE SIDE)	
Cooling water	
The more fouling	
The less viscous	
The higher pressure	
The hotter fluid	
The smaller volumetric flowrate	

2				
TUBING SELECTION				
Service	Size(in)	BWG	L(ft)	Pitch(in)
Water	3/4	16	16-20	1
Hydrocarbon(Low fouling)	3/4	14	16-21	1
Hydrocarbon(High fouling)	1	14	16-22	1.25
Pitch can be triangular or square. For high fouling fluids it is recommended to use the square pitch				

4	
BAFFLES	
Type	Single segmental (widely used)
Spacing	0.2ds-1ds
Cut	20-35%(20% recommended for Delaware method)
Thickness(in)	(1/16)-(3/4)

3	
SHELL	
Type	Applications
E	Standard
F	Two shell pass flow (truly counter flow)
G,H,K,X	Reboilers, Condensers, Coolers
J,K	When low ΔP (shell) is required

3		
HEAD		
Property	Bonnet	Channel
Cost	Cheaper	More Expensive
Prone to leakage	Less probability	High probability
Access	Disconnect process piping and remove from shell	Unbolting and removing channel cover(easier)
Fixed tubesheet		Floating tubesheet
Cost	Cheaper	More Expensive
Prone to leakage	Less probability	High probability
Cleaning	Cannot be removed for cleaning	Can be removed for cleaning
<i>A floating head and U-tubes exchangers can be used when mechanical cleaning is needed</i>		

Shell & tube Design flow Diagram:

5	
NOZZLES	
Shell size(in)	Nominal Diameter(in)
4-10	2
12-17.25	3
19.25-21.25	4
23-29	6
31-37	8
39-42	10

6	
SEALING STRIPS	
One pair/10 tubes rows	

5.3. Aspen EDR:

Aspen EDR serves as a comprehensive tool for simulating, rating, and designing heat exchangers, with a particular focus on shell and tube heat exchangers. Upon entering the interface, the program provides an extensive range of heat exchanger options. However, a prerequisite understanding of heat exchanger design basics is essential, as achieving a solution in your case may be hindered by thermal and/or hydraulic constraints not aligning with the initial conditions.

Encountering cases where a solution is elusive is often attributed to the calculated pressure drop exceeding the allowed limits. In such instances, adjusting factors influencing the pressure drop across tube and/or shell sides becomes necessary to attain a design compliant with client-prescribed over-design limits.

Aspen EDR offers a notable feature allowing design with various constraints, including tube length, tube and shell passes, baffle spacing, tube diameter, and more. Nevertheless, it is crucial to exercise caution when imposing stringent constraints, as excessively tight conditions may impede the program's ability to reach a solution through its iterations.

Being part of the Aspen suite, Aspen EDR seamlessly integrates with HYSYS, facilitating the transfer of data between the two without complications, even when certain physical properties data is not fully provided. This interoperability enhances the overall efficiency of the design process. Notably, Aspen EDR stands out for its expeditious iteration times, contributing to faster design outcomes.

This software serves a multifaceted purpose by offering capabilities for the design, rating, simulation, and cost prediction of heat exchangers. Specifically, ASPEN is employed to simulate heat exchangers designed using Kern's theoretical method. In the simulation mode, users input comprehensive data encompassing the heat exchanger's geometry, fluid properties, flow rates, and input temperatures of fluid streams. Subsequently, the software produces outputs, including the attained output temperatures of the streams.

One noteworthy output is the TEMA sheet, a specification sheet generated by the software. This sheet provides crucial information such as the overall heat transfer coefficient, pressure drop in both the shell-side and tube-side, along with various other parameters integral to heat exchanger design. Additionally, the software offers essential drawings of the heat exchanger, contributing to a comprehensive and detailed understanding of the design. Overall, ASPEN proves to be a valuable tool for engineers and designers involved in the intricate process of heat exchanger design, offering efficiency and precision in various aspects of the design and simulation workflow.

Process and property data can be entered in three ways:

1. Manually
2. By using the physical property databanks provided within the program
3. By importing from a simulation case

We will enter process and property data manually for the simulation of the given problem.

5.4. Process Simulation:

Fig 5.1: Screen shot of the crude distillation unit with heat exchanger E-100 as the basis for rating/checking design calculations from the PFD in the Simulation Environment (Source: UniSim Design R443, Courtesy of Honeywell Process Solutions).

5.5. Problem Statement: A kerosene stream with a Flow rate of 45000 lb./h is to be cooled from 390°F to 250°F by heat Exchanger with 150000 lb./h of crude oil at 100°F. A maximum pressure drop of 15 psi has been specified from each stream. Prior experience with this particular oil indicates that it exhibits significant fouling tendencies, and a fouling factor of $0.003 \text{ h ft}^2\text{°F}/\text{BTU}$ is recommended. Design a Shell & Tube Heat Exchanger for this process.

Fluid property	Kerosene	Crude Oil
C_p , Btu/lb _m ·°F	0.59	0.49
k , Btu/h.ft.°F	0.079	0.077
μ , lb _m /ft.h	0.97	8.7
Specific gravity	0.785	0.85
Pr	7.24	55.36

Tube side fluid	Shell side fluid
Corrosive fluid	Condensing vapour (unless corrosion)
Cooling water	Fluid with large ΔT ($> 100^\circ\text{F}$)
Fouling fluid	
Less viscous fluid	
Higher pressure stream	
Hotter fluid	

Solution:

1. Fluid Placement: Kerosene, being non-corrosive, is suitable for the shell, while crude oil, dependent on salt and sulfur contents, should be placed in the tubes. At lower temperatures, corrosion concerns are mitigated if the crude oil has been adequately desalted. The tube placement is chosen due to crude oil's higher fouling tendency, as indicated in Table 1. Additionally, the shell is designated for kerosene owing to its substantial temperature difference of 140°F.

2. Shell and Head Types: With the recommended fouling factor for kerosene indicating significant fouling potential, a floating head exchanger is selected to allow for mechanical cleaning of the exterior tube surfaces. The floating tubesheet accommodates differential thermal expansion due to the substantial temperature difference between the two streams. Consequently, a type AES exchanger is specified.

3. Tubing: Adhering to design guidelines for fouling crude oil service, 1-inch 14 BWG tubes, each with a length of 14 feet, are chosen.

4. Tube Layout: To facilitate cleaning of the tube exterior surfaces, a square pitch is specified, providing cleaning lanes through the tube bundle. Following design guidelines for 1-inch tubes, a tube pitch of 1.25 inches is designated.

5. Baffles: The Simplified Delaware method requires segmental baffles with a 20% cut. A baffle spacing of 0.3 shell diameters ($B_s/D_s = 0.3$) is chosen.

6. Sealing Strips: In line with the requirements of the Simplified Delaware method and design guidelines, one pair of sealing strips per 10 tube rows is specified.

7. Construction Materials: Since neither fluid is corrosive, plain carbon steel is specified for tubes, shell, and other components.

INITIAL GEOMETRY		
Tube Fluid	Crude Oil	
TEMA Configuration	AES	
Tubing Selection	Tube Size(inches)	1
	Tube BWG	14
	Tube Long (ft)	20
	Tube Pitch(in)	1.25
	Tube Layout	Square
Baffles	Cut	20%
	Spacing (B/ds)	0.3
Sealing Strips	Pair/10 tubes rows	1
Material	Shell and tube side	Carbon steel

File Home View Customize Resources

Clipboard Units **Convert** Set Process Data Set Properties Set Geometry Set Construction Run Stop Run Status Run Control Run Mode Design (Sizing) Find Fouling Rating / Checking Simulation Check Performance Review Spec Sheet Results

EDR Navigator **Console Shell & Tube**

All

- Shell & Tube
 - Console
 - TEMA Input
 - Input
 - Problem Definition
 - Property Data
 - Exchanger Geometry
 - Construction Specifications
 - Program Options
 - Results
 - Input Summary
 - Result Summary
 - Thermal / Hydraulic Summary
 - Mechanical Summary
 - Calculation Details

Geometry **Process** **Errors & Warnings**

Calculation mode: **Design (Sizing)** Recent Previous

Configuration

TEMA Type: B - E - M -

Tube layout option: New (optimum) layout

Location of hot fluid: Shell side

Tube OD / Pitch: mm 19,05 / 23,81

Tube pattern: 30-Triangular

Tubes are in baffle window: Yes

Baffle type: Single segmental

Baffle cut orientation: Horizontal

Default exchanger material: Carbon Steel 1

Size

Specify some sizes for Design: No

Shell ID / OD: mm / /

Tube length: mm

Baffle spacing center-center (Bc): mm

Number of baffles:

Number of tubes / Tube passes: / /

Shells in series:

Shells in parallel:

Overall Results

Excess surface (%):

File created

Heat Exchanger Specification Sheet

1	Company:							
2	Location:							
3	Service of Unit:		Our Reference:					
4	Item No.:		Your Reference:					
5	Date:	Rev No.:	Job No.:					
6	Size :	438 - 4200 mm	Type:	AES Horizontal	Connected in:	1 parallel	1 series	
7	Surf/unit(eff.)	320,7	ft ²	Shells/unit	1	Surf/shell(eff.)	29,8	m ²
8	PERFORMANCE OF ONE UNIT							
9	Fluid allocation	Shell Side			Tube Side			
10	Fluid name							
11	Fluid quantity, Total	lb/h			150000			
12	Vapor (In/Out)	kg/h	0	0	0	0		
13	Liquid	lb/h	45000	45000	150000	150000		
14	Noncondensable	kg/h	0	0	0	0		
15								
16	Temperature (In/Out)	°F	390	250	100	150,57		
17	Bubble / Dew point	°F	/	/	/	/		
18	Density Vapor/Liquid	lb/ft ³	/ 48,67	/ 48,67	/ 52,7	/ 52,7		
19	Viscosity	cp	/ 0,401	/ 0,401	/ 3,5964	/ 3,5964		
20	Molecular wt, Vap							
21	Molecular wt, NC							
22	Specific heat	BTU/(lb-F)	/ 0,59	/ 0,59	/ 0,49	/ 0,49		
23	Thermal conductivity	BTU/(ft-h-F)	/ 0,079	/ 0,079	/ 0,077	/ 0,077		
24	Latent heat	kcal/kg						
25	Pressure (abs)	psi	50	47,39	50	36,62		
26	Velocity (Mean/Max)	m/s	0,24 / 0,52		2,71 / 2,89			
27	Pressure drop, allow./calc.	psi	15	2,61	15	13,38		
28	Fouling resistance (min)	ft ² -h-F/BTU	0,003		0,003	0,0036	Ao based	
29	Heat exchanged	3717064	BTU/h	MTD (corrected)		102,71	°C	
30	Transfer rate, Service	62,69	Dirty	63,71	Clean	109,9	BTU/(h-ft ² -F)	

CONSTRUCTION OF ONE SHELL										Sketch		
			Shell Side				Tube Side					
33	Design/Vacuum/test pressure	psi	58,02 / / /				58,02 / / /					
34	Design temperature / MDMT	°F	455 / / /				455 / / /					
35	Number passes per shell		1				4					
36	Corrosion allowance	mm	3,18				3,18					
37	Connections	In mm	1	76,2	/	-	1	101,6	/			-
38	Size/Rating	Out	1	76,2	/	-	1	152,4	/			-
39	Nominal	Intermediate	/ -				/ -					
40	Tube #: 94	OD: 1	Tks. Average	0,083	in	Length: 4200	mm	Pitch: 1,25	in			Tube pattern: 90
41	Tube type: Plain	Insert: None	Fin#: #/m				Material: Carbon Steel					
42	Shell Carbon Steel	ID 17,25	OD 18	in			Shell cover Carbon Steel					
43	Channel or bonnet	Carbon Steel	Channel cover Carbon Steel				Carbon Steel					
44	Tubesheet-stationary	Carbon Steel	Tubesheet-floating Carbon Steel				Carbon Steel					
45	Floating head cover	Carbon Steel	Impingement protection None									
46	Baffle-cross	Carbon Steel	Type	Single segmental	Cut(%d)	7,34	H _i Spacing: c/c	3,5433	in			
47	Baffle-long	-	Seal Type	Inlet				9,1029	in			
48	Supports-tube	U-bend	0	Type								
49	Bypass seal	Tube-tubesheet joint				Expanded only (2 grooves)(App.A 'i')						
50	Expansion joint	-	Type	None								
51	RhoV2-Inlet nozzle	1813	Bundle entrance	56	Bundle exit	56	kg/(m-s ²)					
52	Gaskets - Shell side	Flat Metal Jacket Fibe			Tube side			Flat Metal Jacket Fibe				
53	Floating head	Flat Metal Jacket Fibe										
54	Code requirements	ASME Code Sec VIII Div 1				TEMA class		R - refinery service				
55	Weight/Shell	1605,8	Filled with water	2300,8	Bundle	737,5	kg					
56	Remarks											

Views on arrow A

Nozzle Data					Design Data		Units	Shell	Channel	Notes:	Company:	
Ref	OD	Wall	Standard	Notes	Design Pressure	psi	58,01	58,01	Location:			
S1	3,5"	0,216"	Slip on		Design Temperature	°F	455	455	Service of Unit:			
S2	3,5"	0,216"	Slip on		Full Vacuum		0	0	Item No.:			
T1	4,5"	0,237"	Slip on		Corrosion Allowance	in	0,125	0,125	Date:			
T2	6,625"	0,28"	Slip on		Test Pressure	psi			Rev No.:			
					Number of Passes		1	4	Our Reference:			
					Radiography		0	0	Your Reference:			
					PWHT		0	0	Date:			
					Internal Volume	ft ³	15,7801	8,0893	Rev No.:			
					Weight Summary				Job No.:			
					Empty	Flooded	Bundle		Company Name			
					3540 lb	5072 lb	1626 lb		City, State			
									Setting Plan			
									Dwg No.:			
									Rev:			
									serth example 1			

Shell inside diameter	mm	438,15
Front head inside diameter	mm	438,15
Outer tube limit	mm	393,7
Tube number (calcs.)		94
Tube number (layout)		94
Tube length	mm	4200
Tube O.D.	mm	25,4
Tube pitch	mm	31,75
Tube pattern		90
Tube passes		4
Tie rod number		6
Tie rod diameter	mm	9,55
Sealing strips (pairs)		3
Baffle type		Single segmental
Centre to outer baffle cut	mm	186,9281
Centre to inner baffle cut		
Impingement protection		None
Shell Side Inlet Nozzle Inside Diameter	mm	77,9272
Shell Side Outlet Nozzle Inside Diameter	mm	77,9272

Notes:		Company	
		Location:	
		Service of Unit:	
		Our Reference:	
		Item No.:	
		Date:	
		Rev. No.:	
		Your Reference:	
		Mfg. No.:	
		Company Name	
		City, State	
Scale:		Tube Layout	
Date:		Date:	
Drawn:		Drawn:	
Checked:		Checked:	
Approved:		Approved:	
Title:		Title:	
Sheet No.:		Sheet No.:	
Total Sheets:		Total Sheets:	
Drawing No.:		Drawing No.:	
Revision:		Revision:	
Date:		Date:	
Author:		Author:	
Checker:		Checker:	
Approver:		Approver:	

References

- [1] Fundamentals of Heat Exchanger Design by R. K. Shah and D. P. Sekulic, published by Wiley in 2003.
- [2] Heat Exchanger Design Handbook by K. Thulukkanam, published by CRC Press in 2013.
- [3] Standards of the Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association 9th Edition by Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association, Inc., published in Tarrytown, NY, in 2007.
- [4] Process Heat Transfer: Principles and Applications by R. W. Serth, published by Elsevier in 2007.